

Figure S1. Calibration factor used to correct the analyzed gas fractions when sampling using the microflow inlet. The correction factor convolutes from two different formulas, which are functions of the total pressure reading inside the MS. Depending on the absolute pressure prevailing at the sample point, the speed with which gas displacement inside the capillary takes place can be vastly different at times. Therefore, a calibration procedure was developed to account for that phenomenon. It was empirically found that pressure inside the MS, determined by an ion gauge, was 3.3×10^{-6} mbar when sampling air (sensitivity factor $SF = 1.0$). The headspace in all headspace measurements after CO_2RR contained an average CO_2 content of around 50%. Calculating from the literature-known sensitivity factors (50% CO_2 with $SF = 1.4$, 50% N_2 and CO_2RR products with $SF = 1.0$)^{1, 2}, this should result in an ion gauge pressure reading of 4.0×10^{-6} mbar. In the case of overpressure at the sample point, air displacement in the capillary happens fast (Ar level detected inside the MS at 0.0% 8 min after switching from sampling air to analyte mixture) and the pressure inside the MS is found to be higher than 4.0×10^{-6} mbar. Since this also leads to an increased ion current from the analyte, the resulting gas fractions were multiplied with a correction factor obtained using formula (2). In case of underpressure at sample point, gas displacement was not sufficiently progressed after 8 min (Ar levels at 0-1% corroborate that fact), and the pressure inside the MS was found to be lower than 4.0×10^{-6} mbar. The measured MS raw data was multiplied with the correction factor shown in formula (1).

$$\text{Correction factor (underpressure at SP)} = \frac{0.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mbar}}{p_{\text{measured}} - 3.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mbar}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Correction factor (overpressure at SP)} = \frac{4.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mbar}}{p_{\text{measured}}} \quad (2)$$

Figure S1 shows the correction factor as a function of the MS pressure reading measured by the ion gauge. The overall correction function defined by formula (1) and (2) is continuous at $p = 4.0 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar.

Figure S2. Calibration curves for different CO gas mixtures using the microflow capillary inlet. CO was quantified at $m/z = 28$ with $E_i = 16$ eV. Analogously to **Figure 3**, the ratio of $x(\text{CO})$ to $x(\text{N}_2)$ was varied, with a constant level of CO_2 at $x(\text{CO}_2) = 50\%$. Purple datapoints correspond to measured CO partial pressures, the corresponding linear fit is suboptimal due to varying pressures at sample point. Corrected datapoints (green) were generated according to the procedure described in **Figure S1**, the linear fit shows the improved linearity after our calibration (function passing through the origin, with a slope of $2.18 \pm 0.06 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar). This function was used to quantify CO in all experiments performed with the microflow capillary inlet.

Table S1. Tabular data of the headspace analysis results after CO₂RR, corresponding to 10 C of charge (see **Figure 4**). Information on how the data was gathered can be found in the experimental section. The overall trend of increasing total amount of products formed for increasingly negative potential can be attributed to the fact that the current density increases accordingly. This leads to a shortening of the electrolysis duration and thereby limits the chance for product re-oxidation at the anode and all other losses, ultimately increasing the gas yield observed.

Electro-catalyst	Potential vs. RHE	x(CO)	x(H ₂)	x(CH ₄)	x(C ₂ H ₄)
Au	-0.8	1.57 ±0.38%	1.89 ±0.52%	0.02 ±0.01%	0.01 ±0.00%
	-1.0	1.43 ±0.20%	2.41 ±0.93%	0.01 ±0.00%	0.01 ±0.00%
	-1.2	1.10 ±0.18%	3.59 ±1.07%	0.01 ±0.00%	0.01 ±0.00%
Ag	-0.8	0.60%	2.95%	0.02%	0.01%
	-1.0	1.21%	3.03%	0.01%	0.01%
	-1.2	3.65%	1.31%	0.00%	0.00%
Pt	-0.8	0.00%	5.45%	0.02%	0.01%
	-1.0	0.00%	4.77%	0.02%	0.02%
	-1.2	0.00%	7.45%	0.02%	0.01%
Cu	-0.8	0.00%	2.36%	0.02%	0.01%
	-1.0	0.12%	3.98%	0.03%	0.01%
	-1.2	0.15%	2.56%	0.32%	0.01%

Figure S3. Mass voltammogram of CO_2RR performed in a three-electrode setup with Ag as working electrode and CO_2 -saturated 0.5M KHCO_3 as electrolyte. The applied potential was varied in a cyclic manner in between -0.4 and -1.2 V vs. RHE with a scan rate of 10 mV/s. H_2O , H_2 and CO_2 were analyzed in standard ionization conditions with $E_i = 70$ eV (a). CO can only be quantified at $m/z = 28$ with $E_i = 16$ eV (b), since the CO^+ trace ($m/z = 28$) in (a) is constant and therefore not suited for quantitative analysis.

Figure S4. Further data treatment on the competing H_2 and CO evolution (which are the only major gaseous products generated as determined previously) on Au working electrodes with data obtained by DEMS.

The H_2 and CO fit functions shown in **Figure 5d** are arbitrarily scaled and baseline-corrected. In order to revert to physically meaningful relative amounts of gases produced during electrolysis, their ratio can be calibrated by the one obtained from headspace gas analysis (**Figure 4a**) at -0.8 V vs. RHE. **Figure S4a** displays the relative fractions of H_2 (red line) and CO (purple line) generated vs. applied potential (obtained through the respective Voigt fits of their averaged signals during DEMS). The obtained results also nicely agree with H_2 and CO fractions obtained by headspace analysis at -1.0 and -1.2 V vs. RHE, also displayed as individual datapoints in **Figure S4a**.

These results can further be correlated with the total current density measured during electrolysis. Neglecting further losses and assuming a total faradaic efficiency of 100% towards the generation of H_2 and CO, their individual current densities can be calculated (**Figure S4b**, grey axis). Transforming these curves into a Tafel-like plot allows one to observe a fairly constant slope for the trace of H_2 , while the Tafel slope for CO changes from a steep value at low applied overpotential to a less steep one at more negative applied potentials. This is indicative of a change in reaction mechanism, or of the rate-determining step.

References

1. Leck, J. H., *Total and Partial Pressure Measurement in Vacuum Systems*. 1st ed.; Springer New York, NY: 1989.
2. Hiden Analytical, Relative Sensitivity - RS Measurements of Gases. [http://www.hiden.de/wp-content/uploads/pdf/RS Measurement of Gases - Hiden Analytical App Note 282.pdf](http://www.hiden.de/wp-content/uploads/pdf/RS_Measurement_of_Gases_-_Hiden_Analytical_App_Note_282.pdf) (accessed 22.03.2023).